

IT TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES, DISTANCE
EDUCATION, ELECTRON DIGITAL EDUCATION

¹Turdiyeva Nilufar Yokubovna, ²Akbarxonov Sarvarxon Saidumarxon o'g'li

¹SamDChTI dotsenti, f.f.n, ¹Samarqand Davlat Chet tillar instituti talabasi

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10816928>

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada xorijiy tillarni o'qitishda zamonaviy IT texnologiyalardan foydalangan holda, ta'lim jarayonida masofaviy ta'limni tashkillashtirish va unda o'quvchilarning faolligini oshirish, o'quv muassasalarida dars samaradorligini oshirishdagi raqamli texnologiyalarning ahamiyati, ta'lim va fan hamda texnologiyani integratsiyalashuvining ahamiyati to'g'risida ma'lumotlar taqdim etiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: IT texnologiyalari, masofaviy ta'lim, elektron raqamli ta'lim, elektron darsliklar, video darslar, vebinarlar.

Abstract. This article presents information on the importance of digital technologies in the use of modern IT technologies in the teaching of foreign languages, the organization of distance learning in the educational process and increasing the activity of students in it, improving the effectiveness of the lesson in educational institutions, the importance of integration of education and science and technology.

Keywords: IT technologies, distance education, electronic digital education, electronic textbooks, video lessons, webinars.

Аннотация. В данной статье рассматривается использование современных ИТ-технологий в преподавании иностранных языков, организации дистанционного обучения в образовательном процессе и повышении активности обучающихся, значение цифровых технологий в повышении эффективности занятий в образовательных учреждениях, интеграция образования и науки и техники. Приведена информация о важности интеграции.

Ключевые слова: ИТ-технологии, дистанционное образование, электронное цифровое образование, электронные учебники, видеоуроки, вебинары.

Introduction.

One of the pressing issues is the application of Information Technology, which, expressing the spirit of the era, is rapidly expanding into the practice of all spheres from day to day, to the process of teaching foreign languages. The Worldwide Information Network is able to provide information in any area for any amount of reception, regardless of the size and speed of information. The emergence of multimedia and Internet technologies has opened a wide path to the use of information technology as an effective tool in Language Teaching and communication processes.

The textbooks that are currently presented in order to radically introduce the educational sphere in our country into foreign languages are also practical proof of this purpose. Consequently, only a student who is interested in his native language and has mastered it can learn it by falling in love with other languages. It is precisely in the next 5-10 years that unprecedented work has been carried out in terms of attention to language learning in our country, and this has been brought to the level of politics, and a number of decisions and decrees regarding the study of foreign languages have been developed in its place. In particular, under the presidency of our President Shavkat Mirziyoyev, a video selector dedicated to improving the system of learning foreign languages was held, and it was emphasized that from 2021, Foreign Language teachers will be

required to obtain a national and international foreign language certificate. Now, instead of constant traditional lesson methods, the organization of lesson processes based on interactive methods using new information communication technologies has been established. In turn, this is also one of the modern methods of learning exactly a foreign language in the developing world. Learning and teaching the desired foreign language using modern technologies is one of the most effective methods.

IT technologies have revolutionized the teaching of foreign languages in numerous ways:

➤ **Language Learning Apps:** Applications like Duolingo, Babbel, and Rosetta Stone provide interactive lessons, vocabulary drills, grammar exercises, and pronunciation practice. These apps often use gamification techniques to keep learners engaged and motivated.

➤ **Online Language Courses:** Platforms such as Coursera, Udemy, and edX offer a wide range of online language courses taught by experts from around the world. These courses provide multimedia content, interactive exercises, and opportunities for communication with instructors and fellow learners.

➤ **Virtual Reality (VR) and Augmented Reality (AR):** VR and AR technologies offer immersive language learning experiences by simulating real-world scenarios. Learners can practice their language skills in virtual environments, interact with virtual characters, and explore cultural contexts.

➤ **Language Exchange Platforms:** Websites like Tandem, HelloTalk, and i-Talki facilitate language exchange between learners and native speakers. These platforms allow users to connect with speakers of their target language for conversation practice through text, audio, or video chat.

➤ **Online Tutoring Platforms:** Platforms such as Preply, Verbling, and Cambly connect learners with language tutors from around the world. Learners can schedule one-on-one tutoring sessions via video conferencing to receive personalized instruction and feedback.

➤ **Speech Recognition Technology:** Speech recognition technology enables learners to practice speaking and improve pronunciation by interacting with voice-enabled language learning applications. Some popular examples include Google Assistant, Amazon Alexa, and Apple Siri.

➤ **Online Communities and Social media:** Social media platforms and online communities provide opportunities for language learners to connect with each other, share resources, and practice language skills. Facebook groups, Reddit communities, and language learning forums foster collaboration and peer support among learners.

➤ **Digital Textbooks and Resources:** Digital textbooks, e-books, and online resources offer convenient access to language learning materials. Learners can access grammar guides, vocabulary lists, audio recordings, and other resources to supplement their studies.

➤ **Language Learning Websites and Blogs:** Websites and blogs dedicated to language learning provide valuable tips, strategies, and resources for learners. These platforms offer articles, videos, podcasts, and other content to support language acquisition and skill development.

Conclusion.

Technology undoubtedly plays a significant role in language teaching, providing learners with unprecedented access to resources, interactive learning platforms, and global communication. It enhances convenience, engagement, and personalized learning experiences. However, it is essential to strike a balance and avoid overdependence on technology, as it may hinder authentic interactions and limit the development of crucial language skills. Language educators and learners

should embrace technology as a valuable tool while also recognizing the importance of human interaction and real-life experiences in language acquisition. By leveraging technology effectively and mindfully, language educationists can harness its benefits and maximize their language teaching potential.

REFERENCES

1. ICT in Foreign Language Teaching and Learning: Benefits and Challenges. Marsida Dedja, Aleksander Xhuvani, University, Elbasan, Albania.
2. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/318539153> ICT in Foreign Language Teaching and Learning Benefits and Challenges
3. Отабоева, М. Р. Chet tilinio' qitishdazamonaviy innovatsion texnologiyalaridan foydalanish va uning samaradorligi / М. Р. Отабоева. — Текст : непосредственный // Молодой ученый. — 2017. — № 4.2 (138.2). — С. 36-37. — URL: <https://moluch.ru/archive/138/39058/>
4. <https://digitalmediakompitentlik.wordpress.com/talim-soxasida-internet-texnologiyalaridan-foydalanish/>
5. <https://www.verbalplanet.com/blog/technology-and-learning-foreign-languages.asp>
6. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/344942969> Digital Technologies in Teaching and Learning Foreign Languages Pedagogical Strategies and Teachers' Professional Competence